

Yuldashev Rustam Elmurodovich

Researcher of the Karshi State University

Annotation. This article describes the experiments in the training of masters of primary education

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Modern theory and practice of education can be understood as "Advising the experience of the previous generations of people and the new generation of" discipline ". In modern society, human be considered and appreciated as professional unity, depends on how much success is developing in its professional area. In this regard, the higher education system has passed into a competition of personnel training, not to extend knowledge and skills, but to form the necessary competence.

The competency approach is an object of study by many researchers, so they considered the concept of "competence" by different.

Thus, in the integrated description of the characteristics of the competent person, higher education is understood as the result of preparing an investor in specific areas or competencies in certain areas or competencies. Because specific professionalisms or problems are shown in readiness to carry out any activities [2; 8;]. In their place, such as competent, competence, reflects cognitive, motivational-valued and emotional-classified.

The result of the computer graduate using a competent approach, the quality of the person is the quality of the person to work successfully, that is, the desire and ability to implement the qualities, and the desires or readiness of personal qualities and readings [7].

The competence is because it is a collection of knowledge or system, in addition to the theoretical and practical knowledge system, also contain cognitive and operational and technological technological constituents.

The competent is a category, which describes a person as a specialized activity subject. The development of human abilities is to do qualified work, to make responsible decisions, make responsible decisions in problem problems, and planning action leads to rationality.

The competent is characterized as a stable ability to have a high level of knowledge and skills [3].

In the broad sense, the competence is the level of study of social and individual and individual activities that allow successful operation in society. That is, in this concept, competence is not as an indicator of the professional ownership of professionalism, but as a more social factor.

According to T.Hoffman, the concept of "Competitive" is open to the visible and defined results of activity, a specific kinds of work to do specific work, [1].

We consider the desire, ability and readiness of competence, the desire, ability and readiness of the competence, to successfully achieving the sets and solving goals in one area.

The current level of development of society, science and technology requires university graduates, not knowledge and skills, but also the ability of innovative creative activity. The period of introduction of new technologies for professional activity is often shortened by reading time, which requires graduates who will find active, non-standard and reproduct solutions. In this case, the second stage is designed to form a leadership and experience of professionalism at the level of master's research [4]. One of the companies that constitutes the system in the training of masters is a research competitor that determines the social and professional development of this person.

The research competency is a set of unique abilities: high level of development of science; Observation and formation of its conclusions in the development rate of modern theory and practice; have research methods; creative skills in finding solutions to the research problem is to demonstrate in such as discussion on the topic of a research.

Stages of formation of research competence in accordance with the submitted abilities:

The first is analytical stage, which is knowledge and skills in the field of science to get acquainted with the methods of research work, search and analyze the necessary information, to learn, to search for the bibliographic sources. This phase is next and the basis for the whole of scientific research in general, the first semester of study is allocated for a master's degree. In addition to the mentioned descriptions, it is developing during the preparation of masters.

The second is a formative stage, including the knowledge of the existing scientific skills, and the ability to communicate in the first stage, among the ability to present their intellectual activities clearly and logically, exchanging views with partners and their partners together. Comparability is strengthened. It is advisable to make the shaping stage with the ability to continue in the second and third semesters in the second and third semesters.

The third is the skills of independent search for the ability of the ability to create scientific and scientific work, thinking flexibility, and conduct research. The stage of creativity can pass in parallel in parallel with the formation phase and are based on analytical stage. The second year of studying in the master's degree must be fully dedicated to its formation.

The formation of research competence is in many ways that is the process of individual characteristics of the individual. This is the most effective way to be able to adapt a strategy to the learner. Therefore, the formation of research competes should be carried out in the process of preparing masters, taking into account the above characteristics.

Analysis of state educational standards in the implementation of vocational training in the master's degree shows that about seventy percent of the competent competence is an integral part of the research competence. Each of them can belong to one of the following five groups: competencies aimed at increasing the general intellectual level; 2 - competencies aimed at developing scientific abilities; 3 -

competencies aimed at developing professional qualities; 4 - competencies aimed at the development of communicative qualities; 5 - Competing aimed at developing creative abilities.

The formation of each competence, which is part of the research competence, occurs in various types of activities, but most of them are formed during the research work.

Analysis of the process of training of masters revealed that only a part of competencies can be formed during training sessions, which is more effective. Thus, the research competency is a base component of masters and should be submitted to them in a practical and applied manner.

The development of this competence is at all stages of education, on the one hand in the study of various academic subjects, on the other hand, the practical - clearly characterized component, in the practical - clearly defined component, in the targeted formation of highlights. At the same time, the main attention should be focused on research work, which is carried out by the master's and a few stages in the educational process and a few stages, each stage shapes certain knowledge, skills and skills. These stages will be published in accordance with the stages of formation of research competencies. In accordance with the state educational standards of the research certificate, each higher education institution has the right to independently determine the border levels of compiling competencies, the right to choose the content and educational technologies. In the process of research, various types of thinking, including logical, systematic, creative and innovative thinking develops. The ability to announce the results of activity on the basis of certain conditions are formed, as well as the flexibility and reflectionability of thinking [9].

The purpose of research work is to master modern methods of working with scientific information, the skills of their analysis, synthesis, use of scientific literature, the use of scientific literature, the use of scientific literature, to acquire research and pedagogical skills, to solve and solve a pedagogical problem. forming skills.

The content of scientific research is classified at each stage of education. In general, it is aimed at forming readiness to professional activity, which later becomes competent and kabby. The initial introduction to research activities includes the study and analysis of bibliographic sources, get acquainted with the methods of research, the formation of research, tasks and problems. The next stage prepares performances in scientific articles, lectures and scientific-practical conferences, allowing them to form logically and accurate and accurate speech, as well as formulate scientific results. Later, in the process of research, masters should learn independently to choose methods of experiment and verification of its efficiency. The results of the research work is a set of results, which is obtained during research, and the author must show that it has the first skills of the scientific work. The master's dissertation should be characterized by the performance of the qualification task as a scientific work. In this regard, the main task of its author is to demonstrate its ability to conduct its ability to conduct independent scientific research and solve clear scientific problems.

Each stage of research work is expedient to use various educational technologies and teaching methods. Usually the responsibilities of the preparation of masters corresponds to more modular, project, context education, as well as active and problematic educational technologies [3].

In the first stage, masters are involved in studying and analyzing bibliographic sources, familiarizing scientific work, forming research hardware.

In the formation of masters, conferences and seminars, the ability to protect the skills, discussions, to protect the skills, discussions, to protect their point of protection, discussion, self-contained skills, He needed to pay attention to the results of scientific work. Problems and design education is playing an important role than teaching methods here.

Participants of the lesson is advisable to discuss one of the current problems of education, the conferences associated with proposals to solve them, "round tables." In addition, holding various forums can produce positive results, while masters will

prepare presentations on their research for a while and reports on the general meetings, as well as protect their projects.

An important element of masters in primary education, leading elements of the industry must have master classes and open lessons with the invitation of representatives of employers and public authorities.

It is important to unite individual and group masters in the final stage of the research work, which includes writing materials and writing a master's degree work.

At the end of the dissertation study, the results obtained at the group meetings should be critical, where special attention should be paid to the methodology of finding out a scientific discussion, formation of opinions, and forming recommendations.

Because the research consists of several stages, the diagnosis of results should be carried out separately in each stage. It is recommended to use a rating system for knowledge control that allows you to assess the work of the master's work. The resolution of the educational functions and assignments aimed at the formation of competencies of teachers of teachers is to play an important role in the formation of competencies and the level of creativity. For each type of work, a student will have a set of points from teachers involved in the work of either a researcher or research.

The final assessment of research skills is carried out during the defense of master's dissertation, while the Master's dissertation will demonstrate the knowledge, skills, and skills received in the training process, including the study.

Relevant conditions should be successfully achieved: the appropriate use of modern material and technical base and literary sources, teaching and technology, teachers, employers, representatives of the state apparatus One, highly qualified scientific and pedagogical staff should work with masters. The knowledge provider is required to change the role of the teacher who goes into a colleague status. The relationship between teachers and masters is becoming more and more and the features of cooperation, joint creativity.

This approaches to the preparation of pedagogical researchers who are able to conduct research in solving modern problems of education.

Thus, in the research work, research competencies will be formed at the Masters, which includes: the ability to analyze, synthesis, optimal selection of research techniques; The ability to build a written and oral speech is logically correct, reasonable and accurately ability; public speaking and qualified communication. Modern problems of education and identification skills to determine their solution; The skills of pedagogological experimental laws; Pedagogical experience and testing of pedagogical practices. Skills in the ability to independently search for creative methods of non-standard professional.

After graduating from the master's degree, the master's degree in education will be able to conduct innovative professional activities in the field of education. The graduate of the second stage of higher education continues to train its education in the next stage - the use of highly qualified personnel and impose and developed acquired skills of scientific activity, and research is a key role in the skills.

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